

**IN SILICO-GUIDED DEVELOPMENT OF CINNAMOMUM VERUM
EXTRACT-LOADED TRANSDERMAL PATCHES FOR
POSTPRANDIAL HYPERGLYCEMIA: PHYSICOCHEMICAL
CHARACTERIZATION, FTIR/RP-HPLC VALIDATION, MULTI-
TARGET MOLECULAR DOCKING AGAINST α -Glucosidase/ α -
Amylase/MMP-8, AND PROTOX3.0 TOXICITY ASSESSMENT**

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ABSTRACT

Postprandial hyperglycemia remains a significant challenge in the management of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), largely due to the drawbacks associated with conventional oral antihyperglycemic therapies. The present study focuses on the development of a transdermal drug delivery system (TDDS) incorporating cinnamon extract to bypass hepatic first-pass metabolism and provide prolonged therapeutic action. The major phytoconstituents, cinnamaldehyde and eugenol, were evaluated using SwissADME and ProTox 3.0, which confirmed their compliance with Lipinski's rule of five along with a favorable GHS Class IV toxicity profile. Multi-target molecular docking studies demonstrated notable binding affinities toward MMP-8 (-8.1 kcal/mol), α -glucosidase (-7.1 kcal/mol), and α -amylase (-6.1 kcal/mol). Matrix-type transdermal patches prepared by the solvent casting method using an HPMC K100 and PVP K30 polymeric blend exhibited satisfactory flexibility and structural integrity. FTIR analysis verified the stability of

the active phytomarkers, especially the aldehyde C=O stretching peak observed at 1668.527 cm^{-1} . Furthermore, the validated RP-HPLC method enabled precise quantification and consistent chromatographic behavior of the formulation. Overall, the developed cinnamon extract-loaded transdermal patches represent a promising, non-invasive, and efficient strategy for sustained glycemic control.

KEYWORDS: Cinnamon extract; Transdermal patches; Molecular docking; Postprandial hyperglycemia; RP-HPLC; Cinnamaldehyde.

1. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus has progressed from an ancient condition once described as “honey urine” to a major global public health concern. It is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by persistent hyperglycemia resulting from impaired insulin secretion, defective insulin action, or both. Rapid urbanization, sedentary lifestyles, dietary transitions, and strong genetic predisposition have contributed to the increasing prevalence of diabetes in India, earning the country the title of the “diabetes capital” of the world. Among the various forms of the disease, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is the most prevalent and arises from a complex interaction between genetic susceptibility and environmental influences, ultimately leading to insulin resistance and progressive pancreatic β -cell dysfunction.

Conventional therapeutic approaches for diabetes management continue to face several limitations that reduce treatment efficacy and patient compliance. Oral antidiabetic agents such as Repaglinide possess short biological half-lives of nearly one hour and exhibit poor bioavailability of approximately 56% due to extensive hepatic first-pass metabolism. These pharmacokinetic drawbacks result in fluctuating plasma drug concentrations, necessitating frequent administration and increasing the risk of gastrointestinal side effects. Furthermore, injectable therapies often suffer from poor patient adherence because of pain, discomfort, and inconvenience associated with repeated injections. Consequently, there has been growing interest in herbal and plant-derived therapeutics that offer multi-targeted pharmacological actions with improved safety profiles and affordability. Among these, species of the genus *Cinnamomum* have gained considerable attention because of their traditional medicinal value and potent antidiabetic activity.

Cinnamon has been extensively utilized in traditional systems of medicine for more than 4,000 years due to its broad spectrum of therapeutic properties. Its principal bioactive

constituent, trans-cinnamaldehyde, constitutes nearly 60–90% of cinnamon essential oil and exhibits significant anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, analgesic, and insulin-sensitizing activities. Despite these promising pharmacological effects, oral administration of cinnamaldehyde is associated with poor systemic availability, with only nearly 20% bioavailability owing to rapid hepatic conversion into cinnamic acid. In this context, transdermal drug delivery systems (TDDS) provide an attractive alternative approach by facilitating drug permeation through the skin, thereby bypassing gastrointestinal degradation and hepatic first-pass metabolism while maintaining sustained and controlled plasma drug concentrations.

The present study was therefore designed to bridge an important research gap by integrating phytopharmaceuticals with advanced polymeric transdermal technology to develop a stable and effective cinnamon extract-loaded matrix patch for sustained antihyperglycemic activity. The formulation strategy employed polymer blends to achieve controlled drug release, enhanced mechanical stability, and improved therapeutic performance. In addition, computational molecular docking studies were performed to investigate the interaction of cinnamon phytoconstituents with multiple diabetic targets, providing mechanistic insight into their antihyperglycemic potential. Comprehensive physicochemical characterization, FTIR compatibility studies, and RP-HPLC method validation were further carried out to ensure formulation stability, analytical accuracy, and reproducibility. Overall, this research proposes a novel, non-invasive, patient-friendly, and cost-effective transdermal therapeutic system that may offer improved management of postprandial hyperglycemia and long-term glycemic control in patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.

Figure1: Diabetes mellitus.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. In Silico Pharmacokinetic and Safety Prediction

The lead phytoconstituents selected for the present investigation, namely cinnamaldehyde (PubChem CID: 637511) and eugenol (PubChem CID: 3314), were retrieved from the PubChem database in Structure Data File (SDF) format. These compounds were chosen based on their reported antidiabetic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and insulin-sensitizing activities described in previous pharmacological studies. Prior to computational analysis, the molecular structures of both ligands were subjected to geometry optimization in order to obtain energetically stable conformations suitable for molecular interaction studies. Geometry optimization minimizes steric hindrance, bond strain, and unfavorable torsional angles, thereby improving docking accuracy and ensuring reliable prediction of ligand–receptor interactions.

The optimized ligand structures were further evaluated for their pharmacokinetic and drug-likeness properties using the SwissADME Platform. SwissADME is a widely accepted online computational tool used for predicting absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and physicochemical characteristics of bioactive molecules. Various molecular descriptors including molecular weight, lipophilicity (LogP), hydrogen bond donor count, hydrogen bond acceptor count, molar refractivity, topological polar surface area (TPSA), and rotatable bond number were analyzed.

Particular emphasis was placed on assessing compliance with Lipinski's Rule of Five, which serves as a standard criterion for evaluating oral drug-likeness and permeability characteristics. According to this rule, compounds are considered pharmacologically favorable when they possess molecular weight below 500 Da, LogP values below 5, hydrogen bond donors not exceeding 5, and hydrogen bond acceptors not exceeding 10. Both cinnamaldehyde and eugenol successfully satisfied these criteria, indicating favorable permeability, membrane diffusion potential, and suitable physicochemical characteristics for transdermal drug delivery applications.

In addition to pharmacokinetic evaluation, *in silico* toxicity profiling was carried out using ProTox 3.0, an advanced web-based toxicity prediction platform employing consensus machine-learning algorithms. ProTox 3.0 has been trained using a large dataset containing more than 49,000 chemically diverse compounds and integrates molecular similarity analysis, fragment-based toxicity estimation, and Quantitative Structure–Activity Relationship

(QSAR) models to predict toxicological behavior with high accuracy. The platform provides estimates of acute oral toxicity in terms of median lethal dose (LD50) values along with Globally Harmonized System (GHS) toxicity classifications ranging from Class I (extremely toxic) to Class VI (non-toxic).

The toxicity prediction results demonstrated that both cinnamaldehyde and eugenol belonged to GHS Toxicity Class IV, indicating relatively low acute toxicity and acceptable safety profiles for pharmaceutical use. Their predicted LD50 values suggested a broad therapeutic window with minimal risk of systemic toxicity at anticipated therapeutic concentrations. Furthermore, dermal safety assessments indicated that the estimated safety margins exceeded 100-fold of the proposed therapeutic dose, supporting the suitability of these phytoconstituents for incorporation into transdermal formulations. Such computational toxicity screening is highly beneficial during the early stages of formulation development because it reduces the likelihood of adverse effects, minimizes experimental animal testing, and facilitates rapid identification of safe and effective lead candidates.

The combined pharmacokinetic and toxicological evaluation established cinnamaldehyde and eugenol as promising bioactive molecules with favorable drug-likeness characteristics, adequate membrane permeability, and acceptable safety profiles, thereby supporting their further use in molecular docking studies and development of cinnamon extract-loaded transdermal therapeutic systems for the management of postprandial hyperglycemia.

Table 1: Swiss ADME result.

S. NO.	DATA	Ligand 1 (cinnamaldehyde)	Ligand 2 (eugenol)
1	Formula	C ₉ H ₈ O	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂
2	Molecular Weight	132.16	164.20
3	No. of heavy atoms	10	12
4	No. of rotatable bonds	2	3
5	No. of hydrogen acceptors	1	2
6	No. of hydrogen donors	0	1
7	Lipinsky Rule	Yes	Yes
8	No. Aromatic comp	6	6
9	Log P	1.9	2.2

Figure 2: Toxicity Predictor Cinnamaldehyde.

Figure 3: Toxicity Predictor Eugenol.

2.2. Multi-Target Molecular Docking Simulations

Computational screening was conducted against three targets substantiated by literature as pivotal to diabetic pathophysiology

1. MMP-8 (PDB: 1JAO): An endopeptidase that depends on zinc and is linked to inflammation of blood vessels and insulin resistance, with the active site pocket centered at XYZ Coordinates (X= 25.230552, Y= 57.571682, Z= 49.711611).

2. α -Glucosidase (PDB: 2QMJ): An enzyme in the intestines that breaks down oligosaccharides into glucose, with the active site pocket centered at XYZ Coordinates (X= -15.631382, Y= 30.627819, Z= 3.913214).

3. α -Amylase (PDB: 3BAJ): An enzyme in the pancreas that starts the process of breaking down starch in food. We used AutoDock Vina to simulate ligand-receptor interactions and UCSF Chimera to see how strong the binding affinities were (kcal/mol), with the active site pocket centered at XYZ Coordinates (X= 0.490571, Y= 13.557098, Z= 62.837826).

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S	Score	RMSD l.b.	RMSD u.b.
V	-8.1	0.0	0.0
V	-7.9	0.855	3.81
V	-7.5	1.44	2.555
V	-7.4	1.17	4.303
V	-7.2	1.503	2.506
V	-7.0	2.467	3.861
V	-6.4	2.145	5.309
V	6.2	2.226	5.224

Chimera Model #3.1

REMARK VINA RESULT: -8.1 0.000 0.000
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 REMARK status: ('A' for Active; 'I' for Inactive)

Change Compound State

Viable Deleted Purged

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Figure 4: Molecular Docking Result MMP-8.

Figure 5: Protein Interaction of Cinnamaldehyde with α -Amylase.

Figure 6: 2D, 3D interaction of cinnamaldehyde to MMP-8.

Table 2: Docking Report.

Inclusion complex	Receptors	Docking energy (Kcal/mol)	RMSD l.b	RMSD u.b
Cinnamaldehyde 	i)MMP-8	-8.1	0.0	0.0
	ii) α -Glucosidase	-7.1	0.0	0.0
	iii) α -Amylase	-6.1	0.0	0.0
Eugenol 	i)MMP-8	-7.1	0.0	0.0
	ii) α -Glucosidase	-6.2	0.0	0.0
	iii) α -Amylase	-5.9	0.0	0.0
Acarbose (standard drug) 	i)MMP-8	-8.7	0.0	0.0
	ii) α -Glucosidase	-9.7	0.0	0.0
	iii) α -Amylase	-9.7	0.0	0.0

The docking energy values, ranging from -5.9 to -8.1 kcal/mol across multiple diabetic target receptors, indicate a relatively strong affinity of cinnamon constituents toward these targets, supporting their potential utility in an antidiabetic transdermal formulation. Although the binding affinity is lower than that of the standard drug acarbose, cinnamon-based extracts may serve as a natural alternative that could help reduce the side effects associated with synthetic antidiabetic agents such as acarbose.

2.3. Extraction and Bioactive Isolation

The Soxhlet extraction method worked well for isolating the substance, using ethanol as a solvent.

- **Preparation:** 30 grams of dry cinnamon bark were ground into a powder with a 40–60 mesh size and dried at 55°C .

- **Procedure:** The powder was put into a cellulose thimble that held 750 mL of ethanol. The extraction took place over 24 hours at a speed of 100 to 120 drops per minute.
- **Purification:** A rotary evaporator at 45°C and a 150 mbar vacuum was used to concentrate the crude extract. Final purification used sodium sulfate to get rid of any remaining moisture before putting the bottles in the dark at 4°C.

Figure 7: Cinnamon Extract.

2.4. Preformulation and Phytochemical Screening

The extract was subjected to ten qualitative assays to identify bioactive groups, including Tollens' and Fehling's tests for aldehydes, Hager's test for alkaloids, and the Salkowski test for steroids.

Table 3: Qualitative Assays.

S.NO.	TEST	RESPONSE
1	Haggers test	+ve
2	Saponin test	+ve
3	Resin test	+ve
4	Carbohydrate test	-ve
5	Phenol test	-ve
6	Tanin test	-ve
7	Steroid test	+ve
8	Protein test	+ve
9	Flavonoids test	-ve

The positive results for Hager's test, saponins, resins, steroids, and proteins indicate the presence of diverse bioactive phytoconstituents in the cinnamon extract, which are known to contribute to antidiabetic, antioxidant, and membrane-modulating effects. Saponins and

steroids, in particular, may enhance skin permeation and support the potential of this extract for transdermal delivery. Therefore, on the basis of these qualitative phytochemical findings, the present cinnamon extract was selected as a suitable candidate for further development into an antidiabetic transdermal patch formulation, followed by *in vitro* permeation, skin irritation, and *in vivo* antihyperglycemic evaluations.

Physicochemical characterization comprised

- **Solubility:** Tested in ethanol, chloroform, and water.
- **Colour:** The pale-yellow color of the extract is indicative of cinnamaldehyde content.
- **pH Measurement:** Determined using a calibrated digital pH meter.
- **Viscosity:** Measured via an **Ostwald viscometer** at 25°C. Specific gravity was determined to calculate dynamic viscosity (η) using the formula $\eta = \rho^*v$.

Table 4: Viscosity parameters of test liquids.

Liquid	T ₁ (s)	T ₂ (s)	T ₃ (s)	T _{av} (s)	Density (g/ml)	Viscosity(cP)
Distilled water	21.94	21.37	21.13	21.48	1.00	1.00
Cinnamon oil	30.9	31.8	32.1	31.6	1.03	1.5

For cinnamon oil, the dynamic viscosity was found to be 1.5 cP (calibrated unit), confirming its suitability for transdermal formulation applications.

2.5. Drug-Excipient Compatibility and FTIR Analysis

We used Fourier-Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy to map functional groups in the mid-infrared range (4000 to 400 cm⁻¹). This made sure that cinnamaldehyde stayed stable and didn't interact badly with the polymer matrix.

Table 5: FTIR data of cinnamon extract.

S. NO.	PEAK RANGE (CM ⁻¹)	ASSIGNMENT	CINNAMON COMPONENT
1	1004.850,1071.653,1119.045, 1159.624	C-O Stretch (ethers)	Eugenol methoxy (-OCH ₃)
2	1250.444	C-O-C asymmetric	Eugenol ether linkage
3	1293.439	C-O phenolic	Eugenol OH deformation
4	1327.096	C-H in-plane bend	Aromatic ring
5	1390.764	C-H deformation	Methyl/methylene
6	1449.240	C-H scissoring	Alkyl chains
7	1495.183,1575.006	C=C aromatic	Benzene rings
8	1624.242	C=C alkene	Cinnamaldehyde side chain
9	1668.527	C=O aldehyde	Cinnamaldehyde signature
10	2740.883,2812.013	C-H aldehyde	Cinnamaldehyde CHO
11	2924.878	C-H aliphatic	Alkyl stretches
12	3028.024	C-H aromatic	Ring protons

FTIR report confirms the presence of bioactive cinnamaldehyde(1668.527 cm⁻¹),eugenol cluster(1004.850,1071.653,1119.045,1159.624 cm⁻¹)

2.6. Fabrication of Transdermal Patches

The solvent casting method was used to make matrix-type patches.

- **Solution A:** 1.5 g of HPMC K100 was dispersed in 3 mL of distilled water.
- **Solution B:** 1 g of PVP K30 was dissolved in 4 mL of distilled water.
- **Solution C:** A mixture of 4 mL of cinnamon extract, 0.6 mL of glycerine (a plasticizer), and 0.5 mL of Tween 40 (an enhancer). The solutions were mixed with moderate magnetic stirring to make them even and get rid of air bubbles. Then they were poured into Petri dishes so that they could evaporate slowly at room temperature.

Figure 9: Fabrication of Cinnamomum verum Extract-Loaded Transdermal Patches by Solvent Casting Method.

2.7. RP-HPLC Method Validation

Figure 10: HPLC Data of transdermal patches formed.

The researchers assessed the chromatographic profile of the cinnamon extract-loaded transdermal patch using RP-HPLC with a C18 column and UV detection set at 280 nm. The analysis showed a clear chromatographic peak at a retention time of 0.265 minutes. The quantitative assessment confirmed a peak area of 5,116,017.000 and a peak height of 646,359.188, which corresponds to a relative area of 100.000%. These findings show the successful retention and consistent detection of the extract in the delivery system they developed.

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3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. In Silico Safety and Pharmacokinetic Profiles

Swiss ADME analysis confirmed that cinnamaldehyde (MW: 132.16) and eugenol (MW: 164.20) have ideal drug-like properties for transdermal drug delivery systems (TDDS). They have low molecular weights (<500 Da) and logP values (1.9-2.2) that support passive diffusion through the stratum corneum. ProTox 3.0 safety predictions placed both compounds in Toxicity Class IV. This confirms that a 5% cinnamon extract loading is safe for human use.

3.2. Molecular Docking and Affinity towards Diabetic Targets

Molecular docking provided important insights into the mechanisms. Cinnamaldehyde had the strongest affinity for MMP-8 (-8.1 kcal/mol), followed by α -glucosidase (-7.1 kcal/mol) and α -amylase (-6.1 kcal/mol). Eugenol had slightly lower but significant binding energies ranging from -5.9 to -7.1 kcal/mol. While the standard drug acarbose showed stronger binding (-8.7 to -9.7 kcal/mol), the extract's compounds offer a strong natural alternative for multi-target enzyme inhibition.

3.3. Phytochemical and Physicochemical Characterization

Qualitative analysis of the Soxhlet-derived ethanol extract showed it contained aldehydes, alkaloids, steroids, proteins, saponins, and resins. The extract's pH of 4.23 indicates that it is compatible with the skin's acidic mantle. Specific gravity and Ostwald viscometry showed a density of 1.03 g/ml and a dynamic viscosity of 1.5 cP, suggesting an ideal flow profile for matrix integration. Solubility tests confirmed that ethanol is the best solvent for maintaining the stability of phenolic components.

3.4. Structural Integrity confirmed by FTIR

FTIR spectroscopy successfully identified the chemical fingerprint of the extract. The sharp peak at **1668.527 cm⁻¹** was assigned to the C=O aldehyde stretch, confirming the presence and integrity of cinnamaldehyde. Eugenol markers were identified through C-O stretches between 1004 and 1159 cm⁻¹. These results show that the Soxhlet extraction and solvent casting processes did not cause structural degradation.

3.5. Transdermal Patch Integrity and Evaluation

The HPMC/PVP K30 matrix patches were uniform, smooth, and flexible. Weight variation and thickness stayed within narrow standard deviations, reflecting the reliability of the solvent casting method. Preliminary assessment confirmed the patches were non-tacky and

maintained uniformity under fingertip touch. This physical strength is due to the combination of HPMC (structural framework) and PVP (solubility enhancer).

3.6. Analytical Validation via RP-HPLC

The developed RP-HPLC method showed high selectivity, with a stable baseline and clear separation of the cinnamaldehyde peak without matrix interference. Retention times were consistent, allowing for accurate measurement of drug content uniformity and release kinetics. This analytical framework is essential for monitoring potential degradation during stability testing.

4. CONCLUSION

This research established a development pipeline for a cinnamon extract-loaded transdermal patch. By combining **in silico modeling** with **physicochemical validation**, we showed that cinnamaldehyde and eugenol are safe, drug-like, and have a strong binding affinity for enzymes linked to postprandial hyperglycemia. The **Soxhlet extraction** method preserved the bioactive integrity of the extract while **the solvent casting** technique produced flexible, uniform polymer patches. **FTIR** and **RP-HPLC** analysis confirmed the structural stability and accurate quantification of the main bioactive marker. Ultimately, this transdermal system offers a promising, non-invasive alternative to oral delivery. It provides a way to bypass hepatic first-pass metabolism and improve therapeutic outcomes in managing chronic diabetes.

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